

Macro- and Micro-context Determinations in the Selection of Texts for Translation

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1. Introduction¹

Fundamental translation studies are inevitably interdisciplinary and they necessarily consider translation, both as a process and as a product, from a cross-domain perspective. When trying to understand the selection and interchangeability criteria, to reframe the methodology and instruments of the act of translating, or when evaluating the result of such a complex act, one has to fit together a great number of linguistic, cultural, historical, psychological, philosophical and sociological inputs. The socio-communicative value of a translated text can be fully revealed and genuinely appreciated only within a multi-branched research that takes into account, beside objective determinations, the subjectivity of the translator as a reflexive nexus between the author's creation and the public's perception.

Translating a literary text is always more than just a word transposition from one linguistic code to another. It also implies trans-editing and transformation of data, both at the level of form and expression. Resulting from a constant balancing between accuracy and acceptability, what is at stake in translation is to assure a smooth and easy reception of the reworked text by the targeted reader. Still, translation is not a completely free creation activity. There are certain implicit constraints that govern and orient the process so that the obtained text is equally meaningful and suggestive as the original.

If the subject of the translation is situated in the contact zone between cultures (Wolf 2007: 3), then its object constitutes a contact zone between people. The worldviews and communicative/expressive skills of the author and of the translator

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meet and generate a hybrid that is sufficiently faithful to the initial source and perfectly comprehensible and eloquent for the targeted audience.

There is always a macro- and a micro-context determining the translation. The macro-context is constituted of various historical, cultural and social objective factors that are unavoidably present at each stage of the reconstruction of the authentic text meaning to be translated, when establishing functional links between contacting languages, cultures and worldviews. The micro-context is determined by the translator's subjective choices, decisions and perceptions, starting with the first reading impressions and ending with personalized formulations or interpretations in the translated variant of the foreign text.

It goes without saying that human translation is a procedure much more complex than an automated straightforward building of language and meaning equivalences. Conscious translation effort implies a projection of individual representations on a given semiotic matrix. Some researchers redefine translation as "invention" or "construction of the Other" (Wolf 2007: 3), emphasizing the creative side of the translation exercise. That is one of the greatest differences between human translation and machine translation, as the machine is *a priori* deprived of imagination, emotional intelligence and is definitely not a cultural subject.

Aiming to observe and analyze the marks and manifestations of the translator's subjectivity all over the translation process, we will start with the selection criteria or eventual reasons that may condition the choice of a concrete work, written in a certain language, belonging to a specific author and treating a definite subject, for translation in another language making it available for a different public.

2. Macro-context determinations in the selection of texts for translation

At a first level, such a choice can be determined by some external circumstances, such as: – *power or dominance*, be it political or economic power conditioning a particular interest and attention to a certain country or nation and its artistic, intellectual goods. Such considerations partly explain the popularity among translators of works signed by American, British, German, Japanese writers etc., as they represent states that exert an influence on a global scale and are often perceived as political and economic development models. To translate the latest literary releases originating from this conventional space of political power, symbolizing the centralization of democracy values, society progress, wealth and knowledge approved at a global level, means to transplant the interests, tastes and norms of the country that is synchronously seen as a model of authority and well-being into the public conscience of the receiving community.

It is believed that discovering and sharing the concerns and solutions reflected in the literary works of these nations, can guarantee a similar success and accomplishment to people who get access to this precious information with the help of translation. It is a question of general contemporary prestige or undeniable weight in common opinion.

An eloquent example of such an international cultural affirmation as a consequence of the country's breakthrough is South Korea. As a result of South

Korea's spectacular economic growth from the 1960s onward, its culture and especially its language and literature became particularly interesting and attractive far beyond the country's borders. When choosing to translate or to re-translate (not from the original text, but from an earlier translated into another language version) a Korean literary work, the translator follows a certain trend, trying to align with a collective favorable perspective.

Speaking about a cultural dominance convention reserving a special status to literary works originating from some precise movements, styles or national traditions which have a generally recognized value and compose the universal heritage, allows to delimit a certain classical book stock that will always be attractive for translations, no matter what. This refers to the case of Greek and Latin ancient classics, as well as to certain French, Italian, Russian literature classics, that are incontestably precious regardless of time and place. The power of these canonical works is timeless, their intellectual authority is over any simultaneous passing approbation. Classical works don't lose topicality for new generations, who view and interpret them in the light of their own interest and life experience. That is why translators are always attracted by these untimely writings promising undoubtful academic excitement and commercial benefits.

In the case of classical works we can also speak about retranslation that keeps these texts in a conventional active directory for translators all the time. Retranslation means a process of new translation of a text that has already been translated into a certain considered target language. Retranslation of significant reference books is always of great importance and interest as it shows the ageing and some eventually outdated features of the previous translations; the permanently increasing knowledge of the source text, author and culture; the power struggles and conflicting interpretations etc. (Mocanu, Dima 2023: 238).

Another macro-context reason that may influence a translator in choosing a work for translation is national interest or intersocietal partnerships.

National interest or *intersocietal partnerships* can determine a certain approach and a systematic nature of translations between certain languages and social traditions. We can refer to concrete examples of a "translation policy" established between a source and a target country/ nation, based on their alliance in wartime to defeat a common enemy, for example. Such a situation refers to strongly promoted translations of Chinese fiction into English, mainly for American readers, during the period after the outbreak of the Pacific War (December 1941), when America and China began to cooperate and fight against Japan (Li, Tian 2021: 1). The US government became actively involved in translation projects of Chinese literature, promoting and strengthening in such a way cultural ties between the two nations. This approach was however an occasional one and lasted only as long as national interests and diplomatic strategies were requiring it.

This same factor explains the Russo-centric Soviet translation policies in many of the countries of the Eastern Communist Bloc that existed during the Cold War. Being aligned with the Soviet Union, at this exact historical moment, many states of Central and Eastern Europe, Asia, Africa and Latin America showed a special interest and sympathy to Russian literature. Translations of Russian literary works were privileged and stimulated as a sign of unconditional friendship between

the concerned nations and the Soviet Big Brother. Meaning to create a kind of “common cultural space” within the bloc, the translations of Hungarian, Bulgarian, Romanian or Yugoslavian authors into Russian language were also present, although in a clearly minor quantity.

In the particular example of the Soviet Bloc countries, the translations flow was mainly unidirectional: translations from Russian language grew substantially during the period of dominance of the Soviet Union over its “satellites”. In these countries, translations of Soviet literature quickly acquired statistical and symbolic dominance, as well as prescriptive force (Popa 2018: 432), but the validity period of this trend was limited and lasted only until the states in question were involved in the Communist intersocietal partnership.

Religion and ideology are also among external factors influencing translation choices and policies. When translation is conditioned by one of these two elements, it refers to creating direct correspondence or “identity” between some religious concepts or philosophical beliefs and some new linguistic sign systems in which they are not initially inherent. Recognizing a text as a “translation” in a religiously or ideologically marked context implies a willingness to accept the construction of identity or continuity between two texts across two separate languages or sign systems (Israel 2019: 323), aiming to connect and join in a more or less uniform community subjects from different linguistic and cultural traditions. In such a way, when Europeans started to colonize countries in southern and eastern Asia, they began to produce Bible translations in the local languages.

Similarly, translation was used in the Soviet Union to impose a supranational Soviet identity. Ideologically oriented translation was meant to facilitate the import and appropriation of the canonical works of Marxism-Leninism, which were used to build the communist ideology (Dmitrienko 2019: 210). Situations of this kind illustrate the manipulative potential translation can have, once it becomes an instrument of the power holders. The main objectives of translation when it is shaped by religious or ideological concerns are to impose precise sacred values or ethical ideals in order to conveniently mold mindsets, even if it implies some misrepresentations or distortions of reality.

Ideologically oriented translation is intended to spread the perceived virtues of a more or less ephemeral modernity marked by a certain doctrine or visionary theory, often appealing to indiscreet control of the translators and systematic manipulation in order to promote some crucial principles and ideals through all available means. In order to serve the ideology objectives, the translators have to be loyal to the Party, to the National Leader or to the country’s philosophical standards that embody those objectives. In such a case the translation choice is dictated more or less intrusively by an authority serving the ruling ideology.

The ethical virtues of the translators adhering to such principles were questioned more than once. The Russian translation theorist Andrey Fedorov spoke about the translator’s “ideological responsibility” in his work *Introduction to Translation Theory* (1953). He points to several features of the translation activity within the boundaries of the Soviet code of conduct. Among these features there is a strict principled and planned selection of translated works on the basis of their ideological, artistic and cognitive value, struggling against any kind of objectivism

and tolerance of ideological phenomena that are alien or hostile to the recipient (Soviet) culture (Fedorov 1953: 85). According to Fedorov, the high level of translators' skill is based on the ideological and semantic accuracy of the translation and preservation of the artistic authenticity of the original text, all these traits leading to an exact and comprehensive translation.

The idea of “partiality” of the interpreter (translator) was developed in the same context by the East German scholar Otto Kade. He openly declared that an interpreter (translator) should process a text with partiality, this meaning an engaged approach to the interpreting from the point of view of the working class on the basis of the Marxist-Leninist worldview (*apud* Pym 2021: 66).

The lately cited examples demonstrate the possibility to use translation as an instrument of a coercive power or regime. Not once in human history, special national programs and institutions were founded in order to promote through the means of thoroughly ideologically regulated translations the states' propaganda, helping concrete persons or furthering certain causes. In this case the translator becomes a mediator of crucial importance in adjusting an original text, potentially having the power to attract foreign readers, in such a way that its translated variant can contribute to fulfill definite social purposes marked by some immediately functional ideas.

Once influenced by religious or ideological reasons the translator cannot be cognitively neutral and reasonably impartial neither when selecting the works for translation, nor when operating the code and meaning transposition. In case this engagements are not a result of a personal decision, the restraining character of the macro-context elements determined by the socio-historical environment on the translation premises and results is vividly illustrated.

Marketing trends and commercial potential of the literary works to be translated indicate to another external reason susceptible to influence a translator in his choices. Nowadays the anticipation of the financial profit an intellectual activity can bring is essential. It is no revelation that literature has become an industry within the modern globalised world. In accordance with the economic logic of this sphere, there is also a business approach in the choice of literary titles to be translated for a mass consumption.

Deciding whether a book is worth to be translated, when the main pursued objective is financial profit and marketability, relies on whether the concerned book fits with some subject of keen collective interest or whether it aligns to the current market. The filtering at this point can be done according to different book ratings, market success reports of big editing houses or commercial platforms, as well as the results of various literature awards and contests. Another important side to be considered includes professional reviews, readers' comments and critical evaluation. Journalists and public persons discussing cultural matters can determine a book's success as well. Nowadays we should also take into account advertising and social media posts that are susceptible to strongly influence the society's cultural preferences and literary tastes.

From this perspective, the first in line for translations are usually the bestsellers, newly released blockbuster novels on one hand, and on the other hand there are traditionally appreciated and always inspiring classics.

The more or less conventional pressure of the macro-context factors that influence the translator during his choice of concrete literary works to be transferred to cultural environment they come from, conforms the translator's work to some priory settled goals, motives and a certain target audience. But what really activates the translator's mission of an ideas and values "ambassador", is his personal, subjective power of evaluating and choosing translation material individually, being directed by intrinsic reasons. Subjective determinations in choosing a text to be translated involve personal, cultural, professional, and sometimes even intimate choices that guide the selection of texts for translation.

3. Micro-context aspects in the choice of texts to be translated

Rendering personally selected works into the language the translator knows and feels best is an intellectual performance valorizing the aesthetic and artistic taste, as well as the creative approach and the courses of action of the translator. Intrinsic motivation or predilection in identifying the texts to be translated gives more freedom and leaves more room for creativity and artistic independence. The summation of different internal causes or motives behind the translator's choice of a corpus to be translated, delimits a category of micro-contextual reasons guiding the specialist in translational activity.

Analyzing the variety of internal, personally conditioned factors that explain a subjective interest or preference for a separate work set apart, or towards a regular series of works belonging to the same genre, signed by the same author or representing a certain period or epoch of the literary history, several different scenarios can be projected as to the specific causes making understandable the translator's choice of a particular text:

A translator's educational background plays a crucial role in the selection of the types of works they choose to translate, as it influences their skill set, interests and areas of knowledge. Language proficiency and linguistic knowledge is a pre-condition and a reference point that delimits a concrete linguistically determined section of the world literature, a certain translator can deal with. A translator's proficiency in both the source and target languages is a central criterion that clearly shapes the translation corpus. It happens quite often that translators are teachers of foreign languages or researchers in the fields of literature, language sciences or cultural studies.

Their teaching experience deepens their understanding of grammar, semantics and stylistic subtleties of a text, which can directly enhance their ability to produce accurate and natural translations. Translators with a background in literature are well-positioned to engage with and translate literary works, as they understand the intricacies of literary style, symbolism and cultural references. Similarly, language researchers may have expertise in understanding the nuances of various dialects, registers, or historical variations in language, which can be invaluable when translating texts from or to languages with complex diachronic or geographic alterations.

There are many examples that illustrate the functionality of this criterion. One the most known is Richard Howard (1929–2022), an American poet, literary critic,

translator and teacher of French at Columbia University and several other institutions. R. Howard is widely recognized for his translations of French literature, particularly the works of Jean-Paul Sartre, Milan Kundera, Georges Simenon, Marcel Proust. His career in language instruction gave him the needed expertise to faithfully render the empirical and artistic messages of these authors' works into English. His deep familiarity with both the French language and its literary tradition made him one of the most respected literary translators of the 20th century. The PEN Translation Prize in 1976 for his translation of E. M. Cioran's "A Short History of Decay" and the National Book Award for his 1983 translation of Ch. Baudelaire's "Les Fleurs du mal" are just some of the distinctions he was awarded with for his brilliant work.

When it comes to less commonly studied foreign languages, the situation is even clearer. Several university professors specializing in Romanian language and literature abroad, for example, have contributed significantly to translating Romanian literature into various languages, including Italian, Serbian and English. These scholars generally possess deep knowledge of Romanian literature, culture and linguistics, which helps them to produce faithful and persuasive translations of Romanian works. Bruno Mazzoni (born in 1946) is a Professor of Romanian language and literature at the University of Pisa, Italy. He is one of the foremost scholars of Romanian literature in Italy. Mazzoni has translated numerous works of Romanian literature into Italian, including works by Mircea Cărtărescu, Ana Blandiana, Max Blecher and others. His academic background in Romanian studies and his deep familiarity with Romanian culture have made him a key figure in introducing Romanian authors to Italian-speaking readers. Mazzoni asserts that translation is a continuous intellectual and linguistic challenge for him, in spite of almost 30 years of teaching Romanian language and literature (Mazzoni 2022).

The professional specialization or expertise of the translator is a key internal factor shaping the choices of the texts for translation. The translator's professional background, experience, and area of expertise naturally generate a set of skills and knowledge going beyond just linguistic fluency and lexicographical accuracy. These factors, allowing the translator to deeply understand some subject matters, certain technical nuances or terminological considerations characterizing various fields, such as law, medicine, education, science etc., can determine the translator to choose literary works with plots related to those fields. As thus, we can cite numerous examples of recognized specialists in various domains who chose at a certain moment to translate and sometimes to comment some important literary works related to their area of expertise. This is the case of the American philosopher and political scientist Allan Bloom (1930–1992) who translated Plato's "Republic" and Jean-Jacques Rousseau's "Emile ou de l'Education"; or of the French psychotherapist Hubert Benoit (1904–1992) whose translations of Hellen Deutsch's work "The Psychology of Women" and Daisetsu Teitaro Suzuki's "The Zen Doctrine of No-Mind" are clearly dictated by his professional orientation.

This same criterion can be extended to *cultural and regional expertise*, involving a particular acquaintance with or understanding of a context related to a geographical area or to a national culture. In case the translator has got the possibility to explore, to understand and to embrace another nation's value system or

worldview principles, they might be more adept at translating works of authors coming from this precise country or culture, just because they can accurately grasp the correct meaning of the subtext, considering the historical context and rebuilding a matching translated text. In such a way, Rosa Bailly (1890–1976), a French teacher and writer whose life was closely tied to Poland and its historical challenges, became an activist promoting friendship between France and Poland, had many Polish contacts and organized trips to Poland (Pytlarz 2006: 71). No wonder, that she translated into French a lot of books of many Polish writers, among them Leopold Staff, Zofia Nałkowska, Stanisława Kuszelewska and others. A similar regional and cultural specific expertise characterizes the translation activity of the contemporary Russian translator Gennady Kiselev (1955) whose passion for Italian language and culture brought him several awards and honours, as well as general appreciation in academic circles both in Russia and Italy. Kiselev translated and published in Russian an impressive number of titles of Italian literature: “An Autumn Story” by Tommaso Landolfi, “Me and Him” by Alberto Moravia, “Something Written” by Emanuele Trevi, “The Merchant of Smyrna” and “The Man of the World” by Carlo Goldoni etc.

Similarly, Danuta Bieńkowska (1920–1992), a Polish translator and scholar, translated a lot of titles of Romanian literature into Polish (ex. “Abu-Hasan” by Ion-Luca Caragiale, “Ion” by Liviu Rebreanu, the poems of Mihai Eminescu, Tudor Arghezi, Marin Sorescu and many others) promoting among her compatriots cultural and literary values of the country that played an important role in her destiny. Having studied D. Bieńkowska’s biography, Nicolae Mareș asserts that she was continuously grateful to the country and to the people who helped her a lot over her time as an immigrant during the Second World War (Mareș 2020: 15). Being a young girl and fleeing the war, Bieńkowska found support and hospitality in the city of Buzău and managed to overcome the most challenging period of her life. Her profound gratitude and sympathy to Romanian people and their culture determined her to translate Romanian literature into her maternal language, fostering in such a way cross-cultural interaction and exchange between the two countries and their communities.

Family background or historical ancestry, another situation to be considered in the context of the cultural or regional expertise of a translator is family background or historical ancestry that can strongly influence their cultural identity and language proficiency. It can also generate a kind of genealogical curiosity that makes the translator drawn to choose for translation authors and books referring to their country or place of origin. The influences of multilingual families with deep ties to particular, regionally determinable cultural traditions can be powerful in determining the translator’s preferences, choices, and even their professional trajectory.

In line with this thought comes the example of the contemporary American literary translator Julia Sanches (born in 1987), who was born in Brazil, managed to keep a special strong tie to this country, even after having moved to the United States at a very young age. Her continuous periodical visits to Brazil allowed her to become integrated into the language and culture systems of this country, so as to grow into a successful translator of the writings of contemporary Brazilian authors.

The titles she worked on include “Twenty After Midnight” by Daniel Galera, “Amora” by Natalia Borges Polesso, and “The Sun on My Head” by Geovani Martins for example. Considering the biographical details mentioned above, it becomes evident that Julia Sanches’ decision to choose for translation the works of Brazilian authors was not a random choice, but a natural outcome of the particular kind of connection she had with this country and its language.

Similarly, Gregory Rabassa (1922–2016), a reputed American literary translator from Spanish and Portuguese to English, worked for the transposition of literary works from the language of his ancestors into English. G. Rabassa was of Puerto Rican descent and was fluent in Spanish. Such facts of his biography as his bilingual background and a wide understanding of the Latin American culture, made him particularly well-suited for the complex task of translating literary works. In the introduction to his interview with Gregory Rabassa, Thomas Hoeksema recalls Gabriel Garcia Marquez’ extravagant compliment paid to Rabassa’s English rendering of “One Hundred Years of Solitude”: familiar with English, Marquez has said that he prefers Mr. Rabassa’s English version to his own original Spanish text (Hoeksema 1978: 7). This extraordinary appreciation eloquently indicates to the fact that a good translation is a real act of artistry, a re-creation activity, the result of which can be no less brilliant than the original work. But such an achievement can be reached only on condition that the translator is able to assure an uninterrupted functional correlation both between two languages, and between two complex systems of extremely subtle traits of cultural identity.

François Cheng (born in 1929), a Chinese-born French academician, author and calligrapher, started to translate Chinese literature into French after a long process of naturalization of over 3 decades. As he himself stated it in his speech to the Académie française in 2003, he first became a Frenchman in law, mind and heart, and only after that he resolutely went over to the French language, making it the weapon or the soul of his creative work. It came to be the language of his practical life as well as of his interior feelings and states (Cheng 2003). In the case of François Cheng, we can consider his translations of classical Chinese poems and philosophical texts as a kind of acknowledgement stage in his experiential learning of French and acculturation process. These steps finally led him to an admirable translingual mastery of poetic wording with narrative and character configuration that harmoniously assimilate not only Chinese and French languages, but also East and West mentalities in his translations (Tsang 2023: 3).

F. Cheng’s natural interest for Chinese literature and culture is the expression of his desire to preserve his Chinese roots and to better connect his origins to his new identity in France. The translation of Chinese texts was and still is for him an occasion to explore and to reflect on his experience of belonging to two different cultures and of trying to build literary bridges between them. When working on the translation of ancient Taoist texts and that of Chinese traditional poetry, Cheng is animated by the desire to translate not just words, but to bring the wisdom, beauty and depth of Chinese thinking to the French-speaking audience, to share some profound truths about nature, humanity, love. The intrinsic determination of this translator to promote and make visible the philosophical and literary heritage of his

ancestry can be definitely taken into account among micro-contextual factors influencing the selection of his translation corpus.

Aesthetic loyalty to an author or a genre can also be a significant factor in a translator's decision-making process when choosing texts to translate. This loyalty often arises from the translator's deep appreciation of the author's work, alignment with a particular literary style or passion for a specific genre. Given what has been said, we find it opportune to recall again Gregory Rabassa and his long-term dedication as a translator to the works of Gabriel García Márquez.

Rabassa had a profound professional connection to García Márquez's works and he translated nearly all of this author's major works into English. He started with "One Hundred Years of Solitude" (1966), one of García Márquez's most famous novels, and as cited before in this article, Rabassa's translation of that book is considered a real masterpiece in the field of translation. He also translated "Love in the Time of Cholera", "Chronicle of a Death Foretold" and many of the short stories of Gabriel García Márquez.

G. Rabassa's long-standing dedication to translating García Márquez's works shows the depth of the translator's commitment to an author. By consistently choosing to translate the works of one and the same writer, Rabassa became the English-language voice of the latter. This example vividly demonstrates how a translator's personal and professional loyalty can influence the configuration of the literary landscape for many generations of readers.

Another example of a translator who constantly prioritized the works of a definite author in his translation list is William Weaver (1923–2013). He is known for his highly appreciated translations of Italian literature, but also for his long-standing devotion, from a translator's viewpoint, to the writings of Italo Calvino.

As a translator, Weaver has established a very precise working relationship with Calvino both as a writer and as a person (Alberti 2018: 223). Weaver recognized that he shared a consuming passion for words and for using them with Italo Calvino, and felt an intellectual connection to his thought-provoking style. Their collaboration began in the early 1960s, and over time, Weaver became the main translator of Calvino's works into English, including such titles as "Invisible Cities" (*Le città invisibili*), "If on a Winter's Night a Traveler" (*Se una notte d'inverno un viaggiatore*), "Cosmicomics" (*Le cosmicomiche*) and "The Baron in the Trees" (*Il barone rampante*). William Weaver really enjoyed the process of translating Calvino's texts, calling it an *aural exercise* (apud Alberti 2018: 223). He explicitly revealed that translating Calvino's writings was a stimulating and rewarding challenge for him, requiring a high level of precision and creativity at the same time. All these confessions emphasize the professional commitment that Weaver felt toward Calvino's works and the continuous genuine interest that attracted him to the particular use of language, philosophical reflections and intriguing themes characterizing Calvino's fiction. This particular appreciation and intellectual compatibility was the basis of the successful professional partnership between the translator and the author, and made William Weaver the so to speak ideal translator for Italo Calvino's literary works.

Personal connections with authors: A translator might choose works by authors they personally know or have a professional relationship with, whether

through previous collaborations or any other kind of personal contact. Having a personal relationship with an author, the translator may feel a deeper sense of responsibility to honor the author's intentions and preserve the features of their voice in translation. This connection can make the translator more invested in the work, aiming to faithfully transmit the author's ideas, symbols or goals.

Personal connections often provide translators with direct access to the author, allowing them to clarify ambiguities, understand context or gain insight into the author's intent. This can make the translation process smoother and more accurate, as the translator can directly ask the author questions or receive guidance on specific aspects of the text in order to conform exactly to the authentic message of the literary work.

In line with these thoughts, there is a definite interest in the example of the German writer and translator Mite Kremnitz (1852–1916) who was a close friend of the Romanian poet Mihai Eminescu and decided to translate his poems into German. The friendship between M. Kremnitz and Eminescu likely played a central role in her decision to translate his poetry. Their relationship, which was built on mutual respect and admiration, seems to have provided Kremnitz with both a personal connection to Eminescu's work and a deep understanding of its significance in Romanian culture. Eminescu was someone Kremnitz deeply admired and appreciated, and she even asked for permission from him to translate his texts (Iosup 2023: 1). Given their friendship and intellectual bond, it's likely that Eminescu was also appreciative of Kremnitz's efforts to introduce his work to a broader audience. Their correspondence on this matter, along with Kremnitz's later translations, reflects the care and respect they had for each other as artists and as individuals. It's a beautiful example of how close personal relationships can motivate a translator to undertake a new translation project and become a source of emotional and intellectual inspiration for both personalities.

A case that is even more special is the relation father-son between Vladimir Nabokov and his son Dmitri Nabokov (1934–2012) who translated many of the works of his father into English and Italian. Vladimir encouraged his son's translation work, and the close bond between them ensured that Dmitri captured his father's intentions in the translated texts. The materials in the archives at the Berg Collection, New York Public Library (NYPL) show that Dmitri's English translations were all done in collaboration with his father and under his father's "responsibility" (Montini 2020: 15).

Dmitri had a deep understanding of the complexities of his father's writing style, which was crucial in translating such complex and layered texts. Their familial connection made him a uniquely capable translator of Vladimir Nabokov's works. Dmitri's relationship with his father certainly added a side of personal devotion to his work, but his skill as a translator was a critical factor as well. It was a combination of emotional connection and professional competence that shaped his approach to translating his father's writings.

The search for the exotic can equally be a strong motivational factor for a translator choosing a work to translate. In this context, "exotic" could refer to the allure of unfamiliar cultures, perspectives or ideas that spark curiosity. Translators may be drawn to works that offer something outside the norm of their own cultural

experience, which provides an opportunity to bring fresh, novel elements into their own language and social context. A translator may be excited to introduce readers to themes or settings that are different from what they encounter in their own daily lives.

An interesting example of a translator who explored Turkish literature with a sense of exoticism and fascination with cultural differences can be Maureen Freely (born in 1952). This well-known British translator chose to work with the writings of Orhan Pamuk, one of Turkey's most successful contemporary authors. Pamuk's novels are often deeply rooted in Turkish history, culture and identity, making it both exotic and intellectually compelling for readers outside of Turkey.

In translating works like "The Black Book" (*Kara Kitap*), "Snow" (*Kar*) and "The Museum of Innocence" (*Masumiyet Müzesi*), M. Freely explored and rendered the colorful and captivating Turkish culture, language and history to bring new nontrivial themes to a global audience. She embraced the exotic elements of Pamuk's writing, not in a superficial way, but as a means to open up dialogues between different cultural contexts. Pamuk's focus on the complexity of Turkish identity, the intersection of the Ottoman past with modernity and the tension between Eastern and Western values made his works fascinating for M. Freely and allowed her to bring a new literary perspective to English-speaking readers.

Through her translations, M. Freely not only helped to introduce Turkish literature to the world, but also captured the unusual flavor of Pamuk's writings, that were not always well-regarded in his native country and even led to political persecution of the author. The challenge of translating works with such cultural depth and philosophical richness likely provided M. Freely with a sense of excitement and motivation. The translator described her determination to promote the ideas and to protect the personality of Orhan Pamuk in her essay "Misreading Orhan Pamuk" published in 2013. In this essay M. Freely explains that she intends not only to make Pamuk's exotic texts *to be understood from afar*, but she also emphasizes the importance of the translator's active position and correct attitude, she asserts that whenever the translator sees literary culture distorted for political advantage, it matters very much that they speak (Freely 2013: 126). And this professional credo should apply beyond any exotic contexts.

4. Conclusions

Translators are artists that recreate cultural messages contributing to ethical and aesthetical exchanges between nations and generations. The choice of literary texts for translation is a very important stage that determines the directions and the outcomes of these exchanges. The selection of translation material is not a random decision. On one hand, various objective factors, such as geopolitical interests and ties, intersocietal partnerships, religious and ideological beliefs, marketing trends, and others, constitute a macro-contextual framework for the translation process and directly influence the structure of the translation selection. On the other hand, some strictly personal and subjective orientations or preferences of the translator can also determine the choice configuration and the course of the translation. Thus, such factors as the translator's educational or family background, their area of

professional expertise or aesthetic loyalty to an author or a genre, personal connections to an author or just the search for the exotic, form a micro-context for the form and content transfer within a literary translation. The analysis of concrete examples of translation scenarios and translators' choices eloquently reveal the impact of the macro- and micro-context determinations on the results of the complex efforts that imply a literary translation.

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Abstract

Translation is a complex activity that should be viewed not only in terms of the process and its result, but also in relation to the various factors that influence it at different stages. The socio-communicative value of a translated text can be fully understood and appreciated through a comprehensive study that considers, in addition to some objective factors that constitute a macro-context for the translation, the translator’s subjectivity as a crucial connective point between the author’s intention and the audience’s perception. In this article, we aim to identify and analyze specific macro- and micro-context factors involved in the text selection stage of translation, providing actual examples and referencing real names to highlight the vast range of potential translation paradigms.